

CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO highly efficient catalyst for the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile derivatives

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Abstract : Mesoporous CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO catalyst was prepared by co-precipitation method. Prepared catalytic material was analysed by means of powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), BET surface area and Py-adsorption FT-IR study to identify the morphology, elemental compositions, surface area and acidic sites. Prepared catalyst was used for the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile derivatives. The synthesis of these derivatives was carried out in one-pot four-component, reaction of aromatic aldehydes, cyclohexanone, malononitrile and aromatic amine. This protocol has several advantages such as non-toxic, non corrosive, clean, easy separation of catalyst.

Keywords : Heterogeneous catalyst, XRD, SEM, EDS, multicomponent reaction, medicinal uses.

Introduction

Versatile uses of heterogeneous catalyst in organic synthesis have been used lot in sustaining green chemistry protocols. Mixed metal oxides have proved to be best catalytic materials due to their ecofriendlyness, high thermal stabilities and reusability over homogeneous catalyst. In the FCC structure of CeO₂, various cation dopants can be introduced in order to improve the physicochemical properties of ceria¹. The acid strength of the mixed metal oxide depends not only on charge but also on radius of the cations². We have selected the transition metal ion as dopant in this metal oxide due to its superior chemical and physical stability, high oxygen mobility, strong interaction with the supported metal and ability to get modified Cs₂O which consist of super base characteristics³. The Cu metal shows redox properties due to its variable oxidation state. The oxide CeO₂, Cs₂O and CuO were commonly used for oxidation⁴, reduction⁵, cyclization⁶, condensation⁷, photo catalytic reactions⁸ and dehydrogenation⁹.

Pyridine scaffold has enormous structural motif that form core of many natural products and in several pharmacologically interesting compounds. Several quinoline derivatives were extracted from natural resources or syn-

thetically prepared in the laboratory for medicinal and biomedical uses. Compounds containing quinoline motif are most widely used as anticancer¹⁰, antifungal¹¹, anti-malarial, antibacterial agents and also used in the synthesis of fungicides, biocides and alkaloids, rubber chemicals and flavouring agents¹².

The preparation of 2-amino-3-cyanopyridine derivatives has been reported in the literature from chalcones on treatment with ammonium acetate via Michael-type condensation¹³, as well as via a one-pot coupling reaction of four components¹⁴ in conventional heating mode or under microwave irradiation and other methods^{15,16}. However, some of these methods are plagued by one or many drawbacks such as long reaction time, use of volatile solvents, low yields and harsh reaction conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to develop an improved route for the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile derivatives.

In continuation of our interest towards the development of new heterogeneous catalyst for the synthesis of bioactive heterocycles^{17,18}, herein we report, CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO catalyzed synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded on Bruker 8D advance X-ray diffractometer using monochromator Cu-K α radiation of wavelength = 1.5405 Å. Conventional scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) were obtained on JEOL; JSM-6330 LA operated at 20.0 kV and 1.0000 nA. The surface area was calculated according to the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method, and the pore size distribution was estimated using the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method by means of N₂ adsorption at 77.74 K performed on a Micromeritics, ASAP 2010. Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were recorded on a FT-IR spectrometer (JASCO FTIR/4100, Japan) in the range 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ as a solvent and chemical shifts values are recorded δ (ppm) relative to tetramethylsilane (Me₄Si) as an internal standard. The UV-Visible spectra were recorded on UV-1800 Shimadzu UV-Spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of catalyst :

A series of CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO mixed metal oxides were prepared by a simple co-precipitation method. An aqueous solution containing the required quantities of ammonium ceric nitrate, cesium nitrate, and copper nitrate was prepared separately using deionized water and mixed together with constant stirring followed by the addition of 20 mL of 5% cetyl-trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) as a structure directing agent. This solution was hydrolyzed using 1 : 1 aqueous ammonia with vigorous stirring until the solution reached at pH 9. Precipitate so formed was allowed to digest at 60 °C in an electric oven for 24 h. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with deionized water, and dried at 120 °C for 12 h. Finally, the dried powders were calcined at 500 °C for 1 h in an air atmosphere. All the pure single and mixed metal oxides were prepared using the same procedure.

General procedure for the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile (3a-d) :

A mixture of cyclohexanone (5 mmol), aromatic amine (5 mmol), malononitrile (5 mmol), aromatic aldehyde (5 mmol) and catalytic amount of CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (0.1 g) was refluxed in ethanol (15 mL) for time mentioned in Table 4. The progress of reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography using pet ether : ethyl acetate as solvent system. After completion of reaction, the reaction mass was filtered, the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure, and the resulting crude product was recrystallized from ethanol to afforded pure product Table 4 (entry a-d).

Spectral data of representative compound :

(3a) : IR (KBr, ν_{\max}) : 3340_(s) cm⁻¹ (N-H), 1500_(m) cm⁻¹ (N-H)_{bending}, 2933_(m) cm⁻¹ (C-H), 2250_(m) cm⁻¹ (CN), 1649_(s) cm⁻¹ (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), 300 MHz : δ 1.09 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.85 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.40 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂), 2.99 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂), 6.15 (1H, s, NH), 7.00–7.05 (5H, m, ArH), 7.24–7.69 (5H, m, ArH). **(3b)** : IR (KBr, ν_{\max}) : 3356_(s) cm⁻¹ (N-H), 1557_(m) cm⁻¹ (N-H)_{bending}, 2951_(m) cm⁻¹ (C-H), 2225_(m) cm⁻¹ (CN), 1614_(s) cm⁻¹ (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), 300 MHz : δ 1.05 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.85 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.45 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂), 2.89 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂), 6.05 (1H, s, NH), 6.90–7.40 (5H, m, ArH), 7.45–7.70 (4H, m, ArH). **(3c)** : IR (KBr, ν_{\max}) : 3340_(s) cm⁻¹ (N-H), 1603_(m) cm⁻¹ (N-H)_{bending}, 2951_(m) cm⁻¹ (C-H), 2212_(m) cm⁻¹ (CN), 1647_(s) cm⁻¹ (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), 300 MHz : δ 1.05 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.65 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.25 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂), 2.80 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂), 6.05 (1H, s, NH), 7.05–7.60 (9H, m, ArH). **(3d)** : IR (KBr, ν_{\max}) : 3336_(s) cm⁻¹ (N-H), 1595_(m) cm⁻¹ (N-H)_{bending}, 2947_(m) cm⁻¹ (C-H), 2212_(m) cm⁻¹ (CN), 1647_(s) cm⁻¹ (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), 300 MHz : δ 1.05 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.80 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.25 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.80 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂), 6.03 (1H, s, NH), 7.15–7.60 (9H, m, ArH).

XRD analysis :

The XRD pattern shown in Fig. 1(a) for pure CeO₂ suggest cubic crystal structure which matches with JCPDS card No. 810792¹⁹. In the Fig. 1(b) the powder pattern of Cs₂O confirms the hexagonal crystal structure which matches with JCPDS card no. 090104²⁰. XRD pattern of Fig. 1(c) confirms the monoclinic crystal structure of CuO which also matches with JCPDS card no. 800076²¹.

Fig. 1(d) shows, XRD pattern of prepared materials, which indicates decrease in intensity due to deposition of CuO and Cs₂O on the surface of CeO₂. The grain size 30.94 and 10.26 nm of pure CeO₂ and CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO respectively was calculated from Debye-Scherrer equation²². Reduction in grain size may be due to CTAB as structure directing agent and smaller ionic radii of Cu²⁺ and Cs⁺ than the Ce⁴⁺. Literature survey reveals that the smaller ions of Cu²⁺ and Cs⁺ are easily incorporated into FCC lattice of CeO₂²³.

In all the composition of mixed metal oxides depicted in Fig. 1(d-f), the diffraction peak at 28.51° could be assigned (111) crystal plane which confirms the presence of CeO₂ in the composite matrix without change in the intensity of peak. The peaks at 35.53°, 38.73° are assigned to (002), (200) crystal planes, indicates the presence of CuO that decreases the intensity of peaks.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of (a) CeO₂, (b) Cs₂O, (c) CuO, (d) CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 1 : 1), (e) CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 0.6 : 0.4), (f) CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 0.2 : 0.8).

SEM-EDS analysis :

The surface morphology of prepared catalyst was studied by SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) images. Fig 2(a) shows the porous morphology of CeO₂, the Fig. 2(b) shows globular agglomeration morphology which is characteristic of Cs₂O. Fig. 2(c) shows rectangular morphology of CuO. A globular particle of Cs₂O gets absorbed into pores of CeO₂ and then after that CuO gets adsorbed on this binary oxide, which helps in the formation of mesoporous material.

Fig. 2. SEM images of (a) CeO₂, (b) Cs₂O, (c) CuO, (d) mixed metal oxide CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 1 : 1).

Elemental composition of CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO catalysts is represented in Fig. 3. The intense peaks in the figure shows the presence of Cu, Cs, Ce and O with 50.41, 10.53, 21.90 and 17.16 atom % respectively. The minimum stoichiometric ratio was maintained.

Fig. 3. EDS pattern of CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 1 : 1).

FT-IR analysis :

The FT-IR spectra of synthesized materials are shown

in Fig. 4. The IR absorption bands at 416, 497 cm^{-1} and 540 cm^{-1} are due to vibration of Cu-O bond²⁴. The absorption band at 1604 cm^{-1} is due to the O-H bending vibration²⁵ and a broad band at 3433 cm^{-1} is due to bridged O-H stretching vibrations²⁶.

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectrum of (a) CeO₂, (b) Cs₂O, (c) CuO, (d) CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 1 : 1).

FT-IR analysis of Py-adsorption on catalyst :

A FT-IR technique was used to identify surface acidity of catalyst, which was performed by adsorption of pyridine on catalyst surface. Fig. 5(a) and (b) shows FT-IR spectrum of with and without pyridine adsorption, in Fig. 5(b) the IR band around 1420–1450 cm^{-1} and 1630–1650 cm^{-1} are confirm the presence of both Lewis and Bronsted acidic sites²⁷ which is contrast with Fig. 5(a).

Fig. 5. FT-IR spectrum of (a) without Py-adsorption, (b) Py-adsorption on CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO.

BET analysis :

The analysis of BET surface area is crucial in aspect to identify the catalytic activity. The BET surface area of catalyst CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 1 : 1) is 36.81 m^2/g which is higher than the other composite materials. The surface area of catalyst increases with increasing percentage of CuO and Cs₂O and average pore diameter decreases as a % of CuO and Cs₂O shown Table 1.

Results and discussion

During the initial study, the reaction of benzaldehyde, cyclohexanone, malononitrile and aromatic amine was considered as model reaction to examine the effect of various solvents, such as methanol, acetonitrile, acetone and ethanol. The best results was found in ethanol (Table 2, entry d), hence, we have chosen ethanol as solvent for the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenyl-amino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile derivatives.

Similarly, in order to optimize the amount of catalyst, the model reaction was carried out in the absence and presence of various amounts of catalyst (Table 3, entry 1-7). In the absence of catalyst, reaction does not proceed (Table 3, entry 1). Pure CeO₂, Cs₂O, CuO and different catalytic ratio doesn't show effective catalytic activity in terms of reaction time and yield of the products (Table 3, entry 2-6). After optimizing the model reaction, it was observed that CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 1 : 1) catalyst is sufficient to carry out the reaction smoothly in short time with excellent yield (Table 3, entry 7). Hence, we selected CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 1 : 1) as the catalyst for the synthesis of the 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)-quinoline-3-carbonitrile derivatives.

Thus, under optimized conditions, the method was further employed to synthesize variety of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitriles and found that electron withdrawing and donating aldehydes reacts without any significant loss in activity to give the desired product in good yield (Table 4, entry a-d). UV-Visible spectra of synthesised derivatives was recorded in the region 400–800 nm. For all synthesised compounds a weak absorption bands was found in the region 513 to 747 nm, which may be due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ electronic transition (Table 4).

The reaction between enolate of cyclohexanone (I) and 2-benzelidenemalononitrile (II) to obtain 3,4,5,6,7,8-

Table 1. Effect on BET surface area at different compositions of catalyst

Entry	Composition of catalyst	Molar ratio	Surface area (m ² /g)	Surface area of pore (m ² /g)	Adsorption average pore diameter (nm)
1	CeO ₂ -Cs ₂ O-CuO	1 : 0.2 : 0.8	28.7	34.0	16.38
2	CeO ₂ -Cs ₂ O-CuO	1 : 0.6 : 0.4	29.0	34.2	18.95
3	CeO ₂ -Cs ₂ O-CuO	1 : 1 : 1	36.8	43.9	13.96

Table 2. Effect of various solvents on the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile derivatives

Entry	Solvent	Time (h) ^a	Yields (%) ^b
a	Methanol	3.5	81
b	Acetonitrile	4.5	76
c	Acetone	5	70
d	Ethanol	3	89

^aAll the reaction were carried out using CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (1 : 1 : 1) under reflux. ^bIsolated yields.

Table 3. Effect of various compositions of catalysts on synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile

Entry	Composition of catalyst	Molar ratio	Yield (%) ^a
1	-	-	NP ^b
2	CeO ₂	1 : 0	NP
3	Cs ₂ O	1 : 0	NP
4	CuO	1 : 0	NP
5	CeO ₂ -Cs ₂ O-CuO	1 : 0.2 : 0.8	6
6	CeO ₂ -Cs ₂ O-CuO	1 : 0.6 : 0.4	20
7	CeO ₂ -Cs ₂ O-CuO	1 : 1 : 1	89

^aIsolated yield. ^bNP = no product.

Table 4. Synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile derivatives

Entry	Ar	Time (h)	Yields (%) ^b	m.p. (°C)	λ _{max} (nm)
a	C ₆ H ₅	3	89	240	600
b	2-Cl	3	81	168	554
c	4-F	3	87	197	747
d	4-Me	4	77	220	513

^aReaction conditions : benzaldehyde (5 mmol), malononitrile (5 mmol), cyclohexanone (5 mmol), aniline (5 mmol) and CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO (0.1 g), at 80 °C. ^bIsolated yield.

hexadihydro-2-imino-4-phenyl-2*H*-chromene-3-carbonitrile (III). This compound further reacts with aromatic amine (IV) by ring opening to get the crude product of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile (V). This plausible mechanism is depicted in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

The reaction may proceed via 3,4,5,6,7,8-hexadihydro-2-imino-4-phenyl-2*H*-chromene-3-carbonitrile (III), which is formed from reaction between cyclohexanone (I) and 2-benzylidenemalononitrile (II), activated by catalyst CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO. Finally through cycloaddition, isomerization, aromatization and cyclization, the desired product is obtained as shown in the Scheme 2.

Conclusion

We have synthesized of CeO₂-Cs₂O-CuO inexpensive catalytic materials by co-precipitation method using cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) as a structure directing agent. Synthesized catalytic materials were characterized by XRD, SEM-EDS, FT-IR, BET, to determine the structure and composition. The nature of acidic sites was predicted by Py-adsorption FT-IR study of catalyst. After conformation, the catalyst was used for one-pot synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-aryl-2-(phenylamino)quinoline-3-carbonitrile derivatives using aromatic alde-

hydes, cyclohexanone, malononitrile and aromatic amine. The present method offers several advantages such as shorter reaction time, simple experimental procedure, high yield of the desired products.

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